

The relation between infinite series,
trigonometric functions and product series.

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ABSTRACT

From the factorization of infinite degree polynomials, and by means of Taylor's theorem, we can arrive at the exact result of infinite summations. We can also establish product series for all the trigonometric functions.

1 Sum of the odd numbers squared.

Let us begin with the summation of the reciprocal of the odd numbers, squared, which is defined as:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2k+1)^2} = 1 + \frac{1}{25} + \frac{1}{49} + \frac{1}{81} + \dots \quad (1)$$

Now, let's express the Taylor polynomial of the cosine of x .

$$\cos(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{(2k)!} x^{2k} = 1 - \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^4}{4!} - \frac{x^6}{6!} + \frac{x^8}{8!} - \frac{x^{10}}{10!} + \dots \quad (2)$$

We can consider the cosine of x , as an infinite degree polynomial, so that has infinite solutions. Let $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ be a constant that can take any integer value.

$$\cos(x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = \frac{\pi}{2} + \pi k \quad (3)$$

Thus:

$$\cos(x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = \frac{\pi}{2}, x = -\frac{\pi}{2}, x = \frac{3\pi}{2}, x = -\frac{3\pi}{2}, x = \frac{5\pi}{2}, x = -\frac{5\pi}{2}, \dots \quad (4)$$

Now, thanks to the fact that we have the lines of the cosine of x , we will be able to factorize it. Let $C \in \mathbb{R}$ be the factorization constant of the polynomial to maintain its original structure.

$$\cos(x) = C \left(x - \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \left(x + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \left(x - \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) \left(x + \frac{3\pi}{2}\right) \dots \quad (5)$$

Next, we will apply the difference squares:

$$\cos(x) = C \left(x^2 - \frac{\pi^2}{4}\right) \left(x^2 - \frac{9\pi^2}{4}\right) \left(x^2 - \frac{25\pi^2}{4}\right) \dots \quad (6)$$

If we give 0 to the x , we have:

$$\cos(0) = 1 = C \left(-\frac{\pi^2}{4}\right) \left(-\frac{9\pi^2}{4}\right) \left(-\frac{25\pi^2}{4}\right) \dots \quad (7)$$

We can see, that the infinite factorization, gives as result 1, so we will go to the identity (6), and divide in the second member by the last member of the equation (7).

$$\cos(x) = 1 - \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^4}{4!} - \frac{x^6}{6!} + \dots = \frac{C}{C} \cdot \frac{\left(x^2 - \frac{\pi^2}{4}\right)}{-\frac{\pi^2}{4}} \cdot \frac{\left(x^2 - \frac{9\pi^2}{4}\right)}{-\frac{9\pi^2}{4}} \dots \quad (8)$$

If we continue developing it, we have:

$$1 - \frac{x^2}{2!} + \frac{x^4}{4!} - \frac{x^6}{6!} + \dots = \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{\pi^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{9\pi^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{25\pi^2}\right) \dots \quad (9)$$

Now we can compare the similar grades, that is, members having the same grade; are equal:

$$-\frac{x^2}{2!} = -\frac{4x^2}{\pi^2} - \frac{4x^2}{9\pi^2} - \frac{4x^2}{25\pi^2} - \dots \quad (10)$$

If we give value 1 to the x , we get:

$$-\frac{1}{2!} = -\frac{4}{\pi^2} - \frac{4}{9\pi^2} - \frac{4}{25\pi^2} - \dots \quad (11)$$

We take common factor in the second member, and we get:

$$-\frac{1}{2!} = -\frac{4}{\pi^2} \left(1 + \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{25} + \frac{1}{49} + \dots\right) \quad (12)$$

If we multiply both sides by $-\pi^2/4$, we get:

$$-\frac{1}{2} \cdot \left(-\frac{\pi^2}{4}\right) = 1 + \frac{1}{9} + \frac{1}{25} + \frac{1}{49} + \dots = \frac{\pi^2}{8} \quad (13)$$

We can conclude that the sum of the inverses of the odd numbers squared results:

$$\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(2k+1)^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{8} \quad (14)$$

1.1 The relation with product series.

If we start from the conclusions we have drawn, we can come to a relation with the product series.

In equation (9), in the second member, we can see how it is formed by an infinite product, so that we can express the cosine as a product serie:

$$\cos(x) = \prod_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[1 - \frac{4x^2}{(2k+1)^2\pi^2}\right] \quad (15)$$

2 Sum of the even numbers squared.

We will use a very similar method to the previous one, but we will never simplify any fraction, at the end of the demonstration it will be understood.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \left[\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{(2k)^2} \right] = \frac{1}{4} + \frac{1}{16} + \frac{1}{36} + \dots \quad (16)$$

Now, I will express the Taylor series of the sine of x :

$$\sin(x) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{(2k+1)!} x^{2k+1} = x - \frac{x^3}{3!} + \frac{x^5}{5!} - \frac{x^7}{7!} + \frac{x^9}{9!} - \frac{x^{11}}{11!} + \dots \quad (17)$$

We can consider the sine of x , as an infinite degree polynomial, so that it has infinite solutions. Let $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ be a constant that can take any integer value.

$$\sin(x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = \pi k \quad (18)$$

Thus,

$$\sin(x) = 0 \Leftrightarrow x = \pi = \frac{2\pi}{2}, x = -\pi = -\frac{2\pi}{2}, x = 2\pi = \frac{4\pi}{2}, x = -2\pi = -\frac{4\pi}{2}, \dots \quad (19)$$

Now, thanks to the solutions of the sine of x , we will be able to factorize it with its solutions, multiplied by two, and divided by two, of course:

Let $C \in \mathbb{R}$ be the factoring constant of the polynomial to maintain its original structure.

$$\sin(x) = Cx \left(x - \frac{2\pi}{2} \right) \left(x + \frac{2\pi}{2} \right) \left(x - \frac{4\pi}{2} \right) \left(x + \frac{4\pi}{2} \right) \dots \quad (20)$$

Next, we will divide on both sides of the equality by x .

$$\frac{\sin(x)}{x} = 1 - \frac{x^2}{3!} + \frac{x^4}{5!} - \frac{x^6}{7!} + \frac{x^7}{9!} - \frac{x^{10}}{11!} + \dots = C \left(x - \frac{2\pi}{2} \right) \left(x + \frac{2\pi}{2} \right) \left(x - \frac{4\pi}{2} \right) \left(x + \frac{4\pi}{2} \right) \dots \quad (21)$$

Now we will apply the difference of squares in the member containing the constant C :

$$\frac{\sin(x)}{x} = C \left(x^2 - \frac{4\pi^2}{4} \right) \left(x^2 - \frac{16\pi^2}{4} \right) \left(x^2 - \frac{36\pi^2}{4} \right) \dots \quad (22)$$

Next, we will make the x to 0 in the first member of the previous equation and solve by the L'Hôpital's rule, and in the second, we will make the x worth 0:

$$\lim_{x \rightarrow 0} \left[\frac{\sin(x)}{x} \right] = 1 = C \left(\frac{4\pi^2}{4} \right) \left(\frac{16\pi^2}{4} \right) \left(\frac{36\pi^2}{4} \right) \dots \quad (23)$$

As you can see, the infinite product containing the factoring constant of the polynomial is 1, so let us divide the second member of equation (22), by the previously mentioned:

$$1 - \frac{x^2}{3!} + \frac{x^4}{5!} - \frac{x^6}{7!} + \frac{x^8}{9!} - \frac{x^{10}}{11!} + \dots = \frac{C}{C} \cdot \frac{\left(x^2 - \frac{4\pi^2}{4}\right)}{-\frac{4\pi^2}{4}} \cdot \frac{\left(x^2 - \frac{16\pi^2}{4}\right)}{-\frac{16\pi^2}{4}} \cdot \frac{\left(x^2 - \frac{36\pi^2}{4}\right)}{-\frac{36\pi^2}{4}} \dots \quad (24)$$

If we continue to develop it, we have:

$$1 - \frac{x^2}{3!} + \frac{x^4}{5!} - \frac{x^6}{7!} + \frac{x^8}{9!} - \frac{x^{10}}{11!} + \dots = \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{4\pi^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{16\pi^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{36\pi^2}\right) \dots \quad (25)$$

We shall now relate the similar degrees.

$$-\frac{x^2}{3!} = -\frac{4x^2}{4\pi^2} - \frac{4x^2}{16\pi^2} - \frac{4x^2}{36\pi^2} \dots = -\frac{4}{\pi^2} \left(\frac{x^2}{2^2} + \frac{x^2}{4^2} + \frac{x^2}{6^2} \dots\right) \quad (26)$$

Now, I am going to give value 1 to the x

$$-\frac{1}{6} = -\frac{4}{\pi^2} \left(\frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{4^2} + \frac{1}{6^2} \dots\right) \quad (27)$$

I will multiply both sides by $-\pi^2/4$, and we have:

$$-\frac{1}{6} \cdot \left(-\frac{\pi^2}{4}\right) = \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{4^2} + \frac{1}{6^2} \dots = \frac{\pi^2}{24} \quad (28)$$

If we add up the result of this infinite sum, and the sum of the odd ones, we get (29) which is the solution that Leonhard Euler brought to the Basel problem in 1735, which moreover, is the solution to the Zeta function of Riemann, for number 2.

$$\frac{\pi^2}{8} + \frac{\pi^2}{24} = \frac{\pi^2}{6} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^2} = \zeta(2) \quad (29)$$

2.1 The relation with product series.

If we go to equation (25), and replace in the first member by the trigonometric function divided by x , and simplify in the second member, we have:

$$\frac{\sin(x)}{x} = \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{\pi^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{4\pi^2}\right) \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{9\pi^2}\right) \dots \quad (30)$$

The second member of the equation above can be expressed with as an infinite product series.

$$\frac{\sin(x)}{x} = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{k^2\pi^2}\right) \quad (31)$$

So we can express the sine of x , as a product series.

$$\sin(x) = x \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{x^2}{k^2\pi^2}\right) \quad (32)$$

3 Other trigonometric functions as product series.

In order to take advantage of the properties of product series to get the tangent, let us go to equation (15), and we will slightly transform it so that the product series starts at $x = 1$, but the result is not altered at all:

$$\cos(x) = \prod_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{(2k+1)^2\pi^2}\right) = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{4x^2}{(2k-1)^2\pi^2}\right) \quad (33)$$

It could be seen that the result does not change, but as the product of the sine and cosine begin and "end" in the same place, the tangent will be the division of the same:

$$\tan(x) = \frac{\sin(x)}{\cos(x)} = x \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{1 - \frac{x^2}{k^2\pi^2}}{1 - \frac{4x^2}{(2k+1)^2\pi^2}}\right) \quad (34)$$

If we develop that cluster of numbers and letters a little, we get:

$$\tan(x) = x \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{4\pi^2k^4 - 4\pi^2k^3 + \pi^2k^2 - 4k^2x^2 + 4kx^2 - x^2}{4\pi^2k^4 - 4\pi^2k^3 + \pi^2k^2 - 4k^2x^2}\right) \quad (35)$$

The cotangent of x can be expressed as $1/\tan(x)$, so:

$$\cot(x) = \frac{1}{x} \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{4\pi^2k^4 - 4\pi^2k^3 + \pi^2k^2 - 4k^2x^2}{4\pi^2k^4 - 4\pi^2k^3 + \pi^2k^2 - 4k^2x^2 + 4kx^2 - x^2}\right) \text{ for } x \neq 0 \quad (36)$$

The cosecant of x can be expressed as $1/\sin(x)$, so:

$$\csc(x) = \frac{1}{x} \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{\pi^2k^2}{\pi^2k^2 - x^2}\right) \text{ for } x \neq 0 \quad (37)$$

The secant of x can be expressed as $1/\cos(x)$, so:

$$\sec(x) = \prod_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{4\pi^2 k^2 - 4\pi^2 k + \pi^2}{4\pi^2 k^2 - 4\pi^2 k + \pi^2 - 4x^2} \right) \quad (38)$$

4 References.

- [1] The Basel Problem: <https://brilliant.org/wiki/sum-of-reciprocal-of-squares-basel-theorem/>.
- [2] Taylor Series: <https://brilliant.org/wiki/sum-of-reciprocal-of-squares-basel-theorem/>.
- [3] Problema de Basilea (Suma de los inversos de los cuadrados) - Euler: January 16, 2016 (MateFacil - YouTube).